

Teaching English with Computer Technology

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Abstract: reference of multimedia media products in English lessons. The process of creating the software of the electronic and educational methodological complex on English lessons, as well as the creation of a computer imitation model. To carry out the process of teaching English lessons in higher education and secondary educational institutions through multimedia tools, as well as to improve the creation of a vertical base in it. Establishing the use of virtual resources in the educational process. The English lesson covers informative and communicative technologies.

Keywords: English, information, multimedia, education, mastering, textbook.

Introduction

A student who wants to learn English, first of all, will have to create an atmosphere of the English language for himself, regularly increasing his knowledge. Without reading, it is difficult to master the language. Reading is the best way to understand. A good reader will be able to understand the sentences and structure of the written text. Bright and Mac Gregor believe that reading is the most enjoyable way to learn and learn the language. Because by studying, the student learns new words and tries to remember. It can be seen that reading is the main factor in language learning. One of the important concepts of developing reading and speaking skills is the use of the language to learn and communicate. Reading can play a large role in successful language acquisition.

It can also improve speech ability. It should be noted that speech plays a very important role in the study of a foreign language, since messages are transmitted through speech. English learners are well aware that there are four skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing). But speaking seems to be the most important of the four skills. Extracurricular reading has the most important impact on verbal communication skills. Students who read a lot tend to speak well. By studying, students develop fluency in speech and the ability to correctly express their opinion.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Reading is one of the most effective ways to learn a foreign language. Reading involves the process by which students discover a new meaning for themselves by combining information in the text and their own basic knowledge. The ability to read requires the reader to receive information from the text and combine it with the information and assumptions present in the reader. Linguist J.C. Alderson argues that reading consists of two components: knowing and understanding the word. These two components, obtained through study, improve students' language skills. Reading increases students' ability to engage in conversation. Reading will help students understand the new words needed for the conversation. Through reading, language learners acquire a vocabulary richness that facilitates speech skills and have the opportunity to develop the structural applications of the language they want to learn. These

components, which are necessary through reading, are necessary for the development of speech skills.

To understand how language works, students need to pay attention to grammar. Reading helps students master vocabulary and grammar. By reading, students see how words fit together. When students are constantly engaged in the target language, they begin to realize and master the diversity in the language. Linguist McCarthy argues that lexical and grammatical knowledge is significantly involved in achieving high performance in reading skills. This means that students achieve a better understanding of reading through grammar. Reading can significantly contribute to increasing knowledge and skills in the second language. There are good reasons to assume that reading contributes to all skills according to general competence. For effective communication, vocabulary knowledge is indispensable. Many linguists argue that learning a dictionary is a key task in learning a second language, and any language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, writing, and translating will not be available without a dictionary.

A dictionary is an understanding of the meaning of a word, so without words, communication does not occur. Therefore, reading, perhaps, the best way to learn new words dictionary is considered to increase wealth. A broad and deep vocabulary helps readers to speak clearly and expressively. By reading, students see how new words are associated with other words. The more you read, the more vocabulary you have that does not enter the oral language. Improved vocabulary helps students develop speech skills. It is impossible to create speech without vocabulary. Vocabulary is one of the important and main components of communication. The vocabulary wealth that students can acquire through reading allows them to improve their speech skills. The habit of constant reading, on the other hand, allows readers to easily understand the text, even if they do not know the meaning of certain words in the text. Reading a lot increases their ability to understand.

The use of information tools in the study of a foreign language, especially English, the production of programs in it also gives the results of the implementation of the requirements itself. Of course, all these are told to a complex of facilities that are able to be used in the educational process as modern programs. Modern teaching analysis of electronic publications showed their autonomy to classification, having a complex structure. On the basis of the classification of e-learning publications, there are general methods of classification of both educational and electronic and software tools. The main type of educational process is a lecture. A lecture is a form of Organization of the educational process that forms knowledge, which is the guiding basis for the educational material that must be mastered by students. There are three main types of lecture, which are introductory lecture, information lecture, and review lectures. Depending on the subject of the studied science and didactic purposes, the following forms of lectures can be used: problem lecture, visual lecture, press conference etc. Enriching the material in which the e-learning publications used in the lectures are described with video tapes, sound animated rollers should help the speaker demonstrate complex processes. When organizing the study of theoretical material, the following types of e-learning prose can be used:

The lecture is recorded using a video camera. The winning side of this type of lecture is the availability of the opportunity to stop at the most recent and difficult places where you can do it again and again.

Interactive instructional programs can be created for Independent Education. When using such tutorials, each student can choose a learning trajectory, optimal learning tempo and method that is convenient for them. The acquisition indicator can also be increased in many ways at the expense of controlling agents.

Electronic lecture texts, base synopsis, methodological manuals on the study of theoretical material, etc. Independent information technology-based education of students includes: working with an electronic textbook, watching video classes, hearing audiocassettes, working on computer trainers, passing a computer test, etc. Currently, all types of knowledge control can be carried out on the basis of specially developed computer programs using electronic educational publications.

Conclusion

The theoretical and practical research work developed on the topic of creation and implementation in the educational process of virtual resources on the basis of information and communication technologies on

the subject of the specialty English has led to the following conclusions.

1. It was founded that the study of the theoretical, scientific and methodological and pedagogical foundations of the creation of vertical resources on foreign languages is an urgent problem. When creating a vertical base, the programs studied were divided and studied with full knowledge of the Flash program.
2. Methodological aspects of the creation of virtual resources created from the subject of the English language were touched upon and justified.
3. A virtual resource was created based on computer imitation models for subjects in the specialty of the English language. Virtual resources were implemented in the process of creation in mutual cooperation with students of other higher educational institutions.
4. A methodology for using the created virtual resources in the educational process in higher educational institutions has been developed.

It can be used when taking theoretical and practical classes in English classes. Therefore, students can also use the electronic educational methodological complex created in this discipline during independent hours of work. This in turn provides an opportunity to improve the effectiveness of the educational process, create conditions for students to independently engage, conveniently and easily organize the data environment, depending on the form of study.

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